

Protocol workshops

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This protocol is used for the workshop methodology within the SPECTRE research project,
<https://spectreproject.be/walkshops>.

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Goal

Evaluating the use of workshops as citizen engagement in Data Protection Impact Assessments.

Why?

The DPIA described in [Art. 35 GDPR](#) requires that – where appropriate – “the controller shall seek the views of data subjects or their representatives” when smart city projects introduce new technologies that can create risks to citizens’ rights and freedoms. However, engaging citizens, and certainly a representation of diverse groups of citizens, is not simple for a variety of reasons. Workshops (‘data walks’) in the city location where new technologies will be introduced may be a method to seek citizens’ views that has a low threshold, immediately visualizes actual circumstances, and leaves room for evaluating alternatives.

Who?

Citizens from a variety of backgrounds. In addition, it may be of interest to organize workshops for smart city managers and administrators, which can address another DPIA requirement: assessing the necessity and proportionality of the new intervention.

What?

Short description:

- A one-hour walk with a maximum of 8 citizens, guided by a facilitator.
- After the walk, a discussion will be held with participants to evaluate their responses.
- Note-takers create a record of the walk and its evaluation.

Extended description:

Phase 1: Introduction

Aim:

1. Introducing the research
2. Introducing key concepts of personal data protection regulations

Preparation:

1. 5-minute speech including:
 - We are doctoral researchers looking into citizens' impressions of personal data collection in public space.
 - We want to include a variety of people and a diversity of responses, so do not hesitate to voice your personal opinion.
 - We will create reports of the walks but will not include names or identifiable information about the participants. We may mention aspects like age or gender when that seems relevant.
 - We are aware that cameras are the most visible way to collect data in public spaces but would also like to know about your response to other types of data collection.
2. 5-minute speech including:
 - An introduction of the smart city concept.
 - A short privacy & data protection knowledge quiz with the following Y/N-questions (to be asked throughout this short introduction):
 - Does someone who wants to collect information about you need your consent?
 - Is your location personal data?
 - Do you have to be informed when someone collects information about you?
 - Do you feel that there are risks involved in the processing of information about citizens?
 - If personal data are collected in public space, those whose data are collected are called 'data subjects' in the GDPR. Data subjects have a number of rights.
 - One important right is the right to information: who is collecting data about you, why are they doing that, which data are they collecting, etc.
 - Data subjects may also have other rights, such as the right to object to processing of personal data, depending on circumstances.
 - When an organization collects personal data at a large scale, it needs to conduct an assessment of risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects. This includes all rights, also e.g. freedom of speech or the freedom to demonstrate.
 - If there are risks, the organization should try to mitigate them, e.g. by minimizing data collection, de-identifying data or short retention periods.
 - In a risk assessment the organization should seek the views of data subjects.
 - We would like to know if a walk with citizens, like we are doing today, can help in seeking those views.

Material needed:

- A hand-out with a small map and a link to more information.

Total duration: 10 minutes

Phase 2: Walking from data point to data point

Aim: Eliciting responses to data collection points from all participants, including responses that are not explicitly uttered or spoken aloud (e.g. emotional responses like anxiety or feelings of security).

Preparation:

- Create a few simple note-taking (steno) principles to refer to data points, types of data collection, and participants.
- Have a list of all known data points on the route with some information about them, e.g. how they function and who operates them.
- Give all participants a number.
- Make sure to have plenty of writing materials, prepared for note-taking on the move and in all weather types.
- **Be alert to on-the-side conversations between participants!**
- **Make sure to also elicit responses from quiet participants. Actively approach them.**
- Identify sheltering places on the route.
- Be respectful: if participants do not want something noted or recorded, don't.

Material:

- Cloth stickers for participant numbering.
- Paper, pens, pencils, slates, plastic sheets, water-proof bags.
- Umbrellas, tissues, band-aids, disposable masks.

Duration: 45 minutes

Step 1:

- Facilitator starts at the first data point (Place Rogier), indicates the devices and starts the conversation.
- Note-takers strategically choose places around participants.
- The facilitators try to give neutral answers to questions about devices.
- While the group leaves, note-takers talk to as many participants as they can reach.

Step 2:

- Facilitator walks to each of the following data collection points but also invites participants to find their own.
- Participants can take pictures/videos of data collection points to discuss afterwards.
- Facilitator keeps track of the time.

Phase 3: Debriefing and discussion

Aim:

1. Evaluating overall impressions.
2. Digging deeper into participant responses.
3. Closing off the walk.

Preparation and material:

- Make arrangements with a café or find another dry place for a group conversation.
- Have a sheet prepared per participant for more elaborate notes. Indicate a few basic details about the participant (approximate age, gender, or whatever seems relevant).
- Have a form ready to collect email address for those who want to be kept up-to-date.

Duration: 30 minutes

Step 1:

- Facilitator starts and leads a 15-minute group discussion. Make sure all participants get an opportunity to speak. If there are children, start with them.
- Note-takers each take notes of the same discussion (for comparison later), but also try to take notes of small remarks or conversations on the side.

Step 2:

- After 15 minutes, note-takers collect pictures or videos that participants made and ask why these were made.
- Note-takers also ask further questions about smileys and other responses.
- The facilitator also becomes note-taker in this step.

Step 3:

- Facilitator thanks all participants for their input.
- Participants who want to be kept up-to-date of results can leave an email address (which will not be combined with their responses).

Route

- Cameras
- Cell towers
- Public wifi
- Bluetooth tracking
- Smart bins
- Fix My Street
- E-scooters
- Smart parking

Data Hubs

Cameras

At Place Rogier, there are various cameras from various controllers: police cameras, security cameras from a hotel, a bank, and an EC office building, and public transport (security) cameras (both on the buses and in the subway). Camera signs indicate what the processing of the video images is based on and who the controllers are, but very little else. For instance, they do not mention what the purposes and legal grounds for video surveillance are.

How can citizens find out about the why of processing these personal data about them? They can contact the controller. They are supposed to receive an answer within a month.

The legal ground for police surveillance is generally 'the public interest'. Private surveillance can be based on 'legitimate interests' but is subject to several restrictions. For example, private surveillance cameras cannot be aimed at the public street, only on perhaps a short distance in front of their premises.

Cell Towers

Different providers have their cell network antennas installed on the roofs. We can see the Proximus head office and some antennas from Place Rogier.

As the largest provider of cellphone network services, Proximus processes a trove of commercially valuable personal data and metadata. They sell data that have been

'anonymized' to a certain extent (e.g. they sell statistics from cohorts), to other businesses (such as banks) but also to cities, who use the data for city marketing. For example, several Flemish cities buy data from cellphone network providers and combine those with data from other sources to create profiles of different types of visitors to the city: one-day shoppers, short-term weekend of conference visitors, longer-term vacationers, etc. The other sources may be publicly available income averages of communities in certain postal codes, credit card spending data, or surveillance camera data.

Public wifi

Public wifi is 'free', but how many people read the fine print to find out whether their online behaviour on this network will be tracked? If such tracking occurs, it may be based on the consent of the user, on legitimate interests of the controllers (e.g. monitoring of the proper functioning of the network), or on the performance of a contract between user and controller. What can be learned from tracking of people's behaviour on the internet is quite a lot: where they shop and bank, which email providers they use, with whom they interact, etc.

Bluetooth tracking

Shoppers are tracked in various ways by various controllers. In the City 2 Mall, shoppers are tracked using the bluetooth signals of their phones. City 2 bases this processing on the 'legitimate interests' of the mall, though that is a dubious application of this legal ground for processing. Probably the purpose of the processing has nothing to do with fraud detection or safety (there are cameras as well for the latter purpose), but rather with commercial interests, such as determining the commercial value of different commercial spaces in the mall – meaning that this information will be used to determine rental prices for shop locations in the mall. Shops themselves also sometimes engage in bluetooth tracking of their visitors, similarly for commercial purposes.

Apart from extensive tracking by various sensors in the City 2 Mall, the city of Brussels also uses bluetooth tracking in the Nieuwstraat shopping area. The purpose appears to be crowd control.

Smart bins

The smart bins in the city center do not collect personal data. They do process data about themselves, mainly how full they are. They communicate those data with the garbage collection service, which will then only come to empty them when needed, reducing unnecessary garbage collection rounds.

Fix My Street

Fix My Street is an app and online service where citizens can report problems in public space, such as litter in the street, broken (traffic) lights, or sink holes. The service is popular, and is also used by city administrators who believe this reporting route works faster than internal bureaucracy. Citizens who wish to report a problem via Fix My Street can leave an email address for feedback but that is not required. They can also upload a picture of the problematic situation which may reveal other phone data, but none of those data are used by the city service behind Fix My Street.

E-scooters

E-scooters are commercial services that process quite a lot of personal data: location data, payment data, and other account data. Some e-scooter services are geo-fenced, meaning that users cannot ride an e-scooter into certain areas of town; the e-scooter will turn itself off. This implies that citizens in those areas of town are deprived of the convenience of e-scooter services and those parts of town are less easily reached.

Smart parking

Parking services, especially the indoors ones like at the Muntpunt, are becoming more and more 'frictionless', in the sense that users are less required to get out of their cars and negotiate computer terminals. ANPR cameras read license plates for automated verification of payment or subscriptions when cars enter and leave the parking area; sensors monitor empty parking spaces for guidance to car drivers entering the parking area; and payment can be done online or via a phone. In addition, smart cameras monitor the parking space for security purposes. The 'smarter' the parking service, the more personal data are processed from car park users. The parking service at Muntpunt also processes a lot of personal data, as is shown at the entrance of the car park, on an electronic board that shows energy consumption and other information about the infrastructure.